

Movement detection algorithm for patients with hip surgery

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Abstract. This work proposes a model of movement detection in patients with hip surgery rehabilitation. Using the Microsoft Xbox One Kinect motion capture device, information is acquired from 25 body points -with their respective coordinate axes- of patients while doing rehabilitation exercises. Bayesian networks and sUpervised Classification System (UCS) techniques have been jointly applied to identify correct and incorrect movements. The proposed system generates a multivalent logical model, which allows the simultaneous representation of the exercises performed by patients with good precision. It can be a helpful tool to guide rehabilitation.

Keywords: Movement detection, Kinect, Bayesian networks, sUpervised Classification System, Rehabilitation

1 Introduction

Currently, the use of online assistance systems is having a great impact on different fields. In particular, in the health sector, assisted rehabilitation has greatly helped to improve the physical condition of patients and to alleviate possible problems arising from too slow evolution.

But rehabilitation usually requires the presence of an expert, a physiotherapist, who must be continuously monitoring the execution of the exercises. This is expensive and it is not always possible. Indeed, the incorrect performance of some physical efforts can be counterproductive for the patient.

This work proposes a system that is able to detect correct and incorrect movements in the execution of rehabilitation exercises. It is based on the application of some arti-

ficial intelligence techniques, particularly, Bayesian networks and sUpervised Classification System (UCS). The proposed model uses the Kinect 2 camera to collect information from patients who have undergone hip surgery.

The main goal is to identify if the patient is adequately performing each of the rehabilitation exercises and to guide them to do it correctly. This has a direct impact on a better recovery of the mobility.

The document is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes some related works. In Section 3 materials and methods are presented (database, pre-processing, and the artificial intelligence techniques selected). Section 4 describes the development of the proposed movement detection system, using Bayesian networks and UCS algorithms, and the final results are discussed. Conclusions and future lines end the paper.

2 Related Works

In general, robotics as an aid to rehabilitation has been studied for several decades. In [1], a recent survey can be found.

The approach proposed in this work is specifically focused on intelligent systems that can help patients to perform therapeutic rehabilitation exercises.

In this line, the work of Akdogan [2] presents the design of Physiotherobot, a therapeutic robot of three degrees of freedom, which is applied to the lower extremities of patients with spinal cord injury (SCI). This system learns specific movements and exercises by a control structure based on rules. The experiments carried out in healthy subjects shown that the robot can perform the necessary movements, as well as imitate the manual exercises.

Schmidt [3] proposes HapticWalker, a multi-center robot for motor rehabilitation. It uses information from 155 patients with non-ambulatory cerebrovascular problems (DEGAS). The proposal reveals that the experimental group has superior ability to march and in other basic activities of life than the traditional rehabilitation group.

The work by Duschau-Wicke [4] presents the immediate effects of training march assisted by cooperative robots, in patients with incomplete spinal cord injury (iSCI). It is shown that assisted training can improve mobility. In this way, patients showed greater temporal and spatial kinematic variability, a greater increase in heart rate and more muscle activity.

In the paper by Kazerooni [5], an improved control model called BLEEX "hybrid", which has an effective robustness when changing the payload, is described. The gait cycle is divided into posture control and swing control phases. The position control is used for leg posture. A sensitivity amplification controller is used for the leg in oscillation.

Jovanov [6] presents a multi-level telemedicine system for applications of physical rehabilitation, assisted by computer and ambulatory monitoring. The system performs real-time analysis of sensor data, and provides guidance and feedback to the user. The system can generate warnings depending on the user's status, activity level, and environmental conditions. In addition, all recorded information can be transferred to medical servers through the Internet and integrated into the databases of medical records and

users histories. This system applies artificial intelligence techniques such as fuzzy logic and self-organized Kohonen maps, obtaining good results.

Our work focuses on the rehabilitation of the lower limbs of patients with hip surgery, applying a synergy of some artificial intelligence techniques to the identification of the correctness of some rehabilitation movements.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Description of the Dataset

To carry out this study, a dataset of four patients who have undergone hip surgery has been generated. For a period of 4 weeks, these patients have received help from conventional physiotherapy and, at the same time, from the proposed rehabilitation tool.

The capture of the movements is done with a low cost device [7, 8], the Kinect v2 camera, while the patients are performing the rehabilitation exercises. The Kinect sensor is essentially a camera that can detect body movement information in depth. When a person is within its field of vision, it internally determines the basic skeleton. That is, it creates a 3D skeleton model that represents the extremities and how they are interconnected. The skeleton of Kinect v2 consists of 25 articulations with their respective coordinates (x, y, z), distributed throughout the body (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Body points detected by the Kinect 2 for Xbox One (MSDN Microsoft).

The data set consists of 3292 samples with 75 attributes, divided into 4 users as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of data by user

User	Exercise 1	Exercise 2	Total samples
1	364	459	823
2	486	345	831

3	301	408	709
4	461	468	929
Total			3292

That is, when training the detection system for exercise 1, the first column is considered as correct samples, and all the data that corresponds to the exercise 2 are use as incorrect ones. And vice versa.

For rehabilitation there is a variety of exercises that the patient must perform, for instance, side step, front step, knee lift, leg lift, rotating hip movement, etc. In this first approach we have selected only two of them, that are considered key exercises for patient's functional movement recovery. The model will be further developed with more exercises once the methodology here proposed is validated.

These two physiotherapeutic exercises are: side step and knee elevation with one and another leg (Figure 2). The objective of our system is to measure the movement characteristics during the execution of the exercise: elevation or distance from the starting point. For the present case, it is not necessary to take into account the speed, strength or intensity of the execution of the exercise, because the rehabilitation focuses on movements that help to give more elasticity to the muscles surrounding the hip.

Fig. 2. Rehabilitation exercises: "Side step" (left) and "Knee lift" (right).

The Kinect camera captures the body movements efficiently at a distance of 2 meters, generating the skeleton images shown in figure 3. The sensor provides detailed information of the movements, angles, etc.

Fig. 3. Skeleton of points captured by the Kinect, exercises of "Side step" (left) and "Knee elevation" (right)

3.2 Attribute Selection

To facilitate the detection of the movements, it was necessary to apply a pre-processing to the data consisting of selecting the most relevant attributes, normalizing the information, and eliminating noise and inconsistent values in the measurements.

The selection of attributes is done using the Greedy Stepwise algorithm, which performs an exhaustive forward or backward search through the space of attribute subsets [9]. The algorithm could start with none or all of the attributes, or from an arbitrary point in the space. The algorithm stops when the addition or deletion of any remaining attribute results in a decrease in the evaluation (1). It can also produce a classified list of attributes by crossing the space from one side to the other and it records the order in which the attributes are selected [10].

$$Goodness_attribute_subset = \frac{\sum_{all\ attributes\ x} C(x, class)}{\sqrt{\sum_{all\ attributes\ x} \sum_{all\ attributes\ y} C(x, y)}} \quad (1)$$

As a result of the application of this algorithm, 18 relevant characteristics are selected (in our case only exercises centered on the hip and on the lower extremities, legs and feet, are considered). Specifically, these attributes are 0y, 6x, 6y, 10x, 10y, 12x, 12y, 13x, 13y, 14x, 14y, 15x, 15y, 16x, 16y, 17x, 17y, 19x, where the number corresponds to the sensor (Figure 1). That is, these attributes identify the coordinates (x, y) of the movement of the lower limbs that will allow the detection of the correctness of movements.

3.3 Classification techniques

Four different artificial intelligence techniques were tested to select the most suitable for this application.

3.3.1 Bayesian Networks

It is a probabilistic graphical model that represents a set of random variables and their conditional dependencies through a directed acyclic graph. The nodes represent random variables, which can be observable quantities, latent variables, unknown parameters or hypotheses. The edges describe the conditional dependencies, where each node has an associated probability function x , which takes as input a particular set of values of the parent variables of the node, and returns the probability of the variable represented by the node [11]. The joint probability density function can be written as a product of the individual density functions, which are conditioned to the variables of their parents (2), where X is a Bayesian network with respect to graph G .

$$(x) = \prod_{v \in V} p(X_v | X_{pa(v)}) \quad (2)$$

In our case, a Bayesian network has been used to obtain the conditioned probability of the movement of each point of the left and right legs while performing the lateral step exercise and knee elevation. It will be compared with the pattern to identify if the movement is correct depending on a threshold.

3.3.2 sUpervised Classifier System (UCS)

The sUpervised Classifier System (UCS) is an automatic learning method based on rules derived from XCS [12]. It uses a genetic algorithm (discovery component) to perform learning tasks. This technique seeks to identify a set of context-dependent rules, which are stored and applied in a distributed manner, to establish behavior models, classification, data extraction, regression, approximation function and game strategy. This approach allows the division of complex solution spaces into smaller and simpler parts.

UCS develops from an initial population of individuals, P . Each initial individual is a classifier that consists of a rule, with a set of parameters that estimate the quality of that rule. A rule has the structure $condition \rightarrow class$, where the condition specifies the set of examples that will be classified with the class learned in the rule. The equation to select by votes each classifier of the UCS algorithm from a population P is given by (3).

$$dv = \begin{cases} ns \frac{F}{\bar{F}} & \text{if } exp > \theta_{del} \text{ and } F < \delta \bar{F} \\ ns & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where ns is the initial dataset, F the individual fitness function, \bar{F} is the fitness average of the whole population P , and θ_{del} and δ are parameters set by the user [13].

In our case, the mobility ranges for each of the selected attributes (defined as correct or incorrect) were considered as the initial population. Subsequently, the algorithm was trained so that it learned to identify the execution of the movements.

3.3.3 Decision tree C4.5

Decision trees are one of the most widely used classification methods in machine learning, especially on unbalanced datasets. They have some similarity with the flow diagrams. Its operation consists in continuously forming partitions of the data set based on a criterion until the final partitions contain elements of a single class [14].

3.3.4 Fuzzy Unordered Rule Induction Algorithm (FURIA)

FURIA (Fuzzy Unordered Rule Induction Algorithm) is a novel classification method based on rules and developed from the well-known RIPPER algorithm [15, 16]. Based on fuzzy logic, FURIA uses simple and interpretable rules, as well as a series of modi-

fications and extensions. The FURIA algorithm learns fuzzy rules instead of conventional rules, and unordered rule sets instead of rule lists, as presented in the following pseudo-code (Algorithm 1):

Algorithm 1: Furia Algorithm pseudo-code

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1: Let  $A$  be the set of numeric antecedents of  $r$ 
2: while  $A \neq \emptyset$  do
3:    $a_{\max} \leftarrow \text{null}$  ( $a_{\max}$  denotes the antecedent with the highest purity)
4:    $\text{pur}_{\max} \leftarrow 0$  ( $\text{pur}_{\max}$  is the highest purity value, so far)
5:   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $\text{size}(A)$  do
6:     compute the best fuzzification of  $A[i]$  in terms of purity
7:      $\text{pur}_{A[i]} \leftarrow$  be the purity of this best fuzzification
8:     if  $\text{pur}_{A[i]} > \text{pur}_{\max}$  then
9:        $\text{pur}_{\max} \leftarrow \text{pur}_{A[i]}$ 
10:       $a_{\max} \leftarrow A[i]$ 
11:     end if
12:   end for
13:    $A \leftarrow A \setminus a_{\max}$ 
14:   Update  $r$  with  $a_{\max}$ 
15: end while

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In the algorithm, $a \in A$ is the antecedent of a rule r , that is, the attribute that is evaluated. Then the attribute with the highest purity is computing.

This algorithm was applied to the movement rules for each of the points given by the sensors (coordinates), using the maximum and minimum limits.

3.4 Selection of classification techniques

Each of these intelligent techniques has been applied to the dataset of Iris in order to compute the most efficient one. The results are shown in Table 2, with the number of correctly (CC%) and incorrectly classified (IC%). The entire dataset of each patient was used for the training and testing, applying the k-fold cross validation technique with $k = 10$.

Table 2. Detection of movements with different classification algorithms.

Algorithm	Training		Tests	
	CC%	IC%	CC%	IC%
Bayesian network	100%	0%	99.99%	0.01%
UCS	99.98%	0.02%	98.17%	1.83%
C4.5	99.64%	0.36%	96.47%	3.53%
FURIA	99.87%	0.13%	98.78%	0.12%

As it can be seen in Table 1, Bayesian Networks algorithm gives the best results, followed by the UCS algorithm. Thus, both of them will be applied and the other two, C4.5 and FURIA, are discarded due to their higher error ratio, even if the results are not so bad.

4 Movement detection model and discussion of the results

The proposed model uses the two selected classification techniques, Bayesian Networks and UCS, in parallel (Figure 4), for both the "Side Step" and "Knee Lift" exercises. The experiment has been developed with a dataset with 1248 correct samples and 1221 incorrect samples for training. For the tests we have used 364 correct samples and 459 incorrect samples.

Fig. 4. Detection model for "Side step" and "Knee lift" rehabilitation exercises

Bayesian Networks are applied to the right leg and the UCS algorithm to the left leg. The 0y point (center of gravity of the patient) belongs to both limbs. The response of the proposed model is unique for each exercise, since the output is correct or incorrect whatever the leg or the exercise. These results are described in detailed and discussed.

4.1 "Side Step" model

The correct identification of the side step exercise for the right leg (Bayesian networks) reaches 98.90% of hits, true positive rate (TP) of 98.90% and false positive (FP) rate 0.90%. For the left leg (UCS), 99.95% samples are correctly classified; TP = 99.90% and FP = 0.24%. Table 3 presents the confusion matrices.

Table 3. Confusion matrix "side step" exercise.

	Bayesian		UCS	
	Correct	Incorrect	Correct	Incorrect
Correct	363	1	363	1
Incorrect	8	451	1	458

4.2 "Knee Lift" model

The correct identification of the knee lift exercise for the right leg (Bayesian networks) reaches 98.66% of hits, TP = 98.70% and FP = 1.20%. For the left leg (UCS), 99.99% samples are correctly classified; TP = 99.90% and FP = 0.12%. Table 4 presents the confusion matrices.

Table 4. Confusion matrix "knee lift" exercise.

	Bayesian		UCS	
	Correct	Incorrect	Correct	Incorrect
Correct	451	8	459	0
Incorrect	3	361	1	363

The results obtained in the testing phase gave an average of 99.34% accuracy and an average percentage of false positives of 0.61%. These results show that the proposed model gives slightly better results than the work by Rybarczyk [7], where the model accuracy in the capture of movements, using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), was 98%.

5 Conclusions and future work

In this work we have developed a model for the detection of correct and incorrect movements in the execution of rehabilitation exercises in patients with hip surgery. The work uses information from several patients in rehabilitation phase, executing two exercises: "Side step" and "Knee lift".

Movements were captured by a Kinect sensor and different artificial intelligence techniques were used to identify the correctness. The combination of Bayesian networks and UCS has been proved very effective.

The proposed model was developed for specific exercises with the idea of generalizing it to other movements. Another future works includes the automatic processing of the movements.

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